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Unveiling Museums' Online Reputation. The Case of the Uffizi Galleries

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Abstract

The museum's reputation is a crucial intangible asset that enables it to stand out in a competitive environment by influencing perceived organizational effectiveness and attracting resources. Specifically, reputation impacts the attitudes of potential visitors towards visiting the museum and the perspectives of donors and sponsors towards funding cultural activities.

With the rise of the Internet and the subsequent proliferation of online newspapers, social media, blogs, forums, and information-sharing platforms, the concept of reputation has expanded into the digital realm. Online conversations serve as proxies for public opinion and, consequently, for online reputation. Therefore, analyzing online public discourse can provide essential insights into the community's perceptions of online reputation.

Despite the significance of offline and online reputation for a museum's sustainability, the literature on this topic is still in its early stages. To address this gap, this research presents a preliminary exploration of the literature on museums' reputation with a twofold objective: (1) review the literature debate on reputation and museums' online reputation; (2) construct a framework from the literature review for exploring the online reputation of the Uffizi Galleries, one of the most visited museums in Italy, located in the city of art of Florence.

This research contributes empirically to the literature on museum management, shedding light on the concept of reputation as an intangible capital crucial for a museum's perpetuation of its mission and sustainability. The findings hold implications for museums' communication strategies, emphasizing how increased online visibility through institutional communication can influence their reputation. Finally, it underscores the importance of measuring and managing a museum's reputation for its sustainability, influencing potential visitors' decisions and donors' and sponsors' attitudes towards funding cultural activities.

Key words: reputation; online reputation; museums; Uffizi Galleries; Florence; city of art

Framing of the research. *The concept of reputation is gaining significance across various organizational categories, encompassing firms, nonprofit organizations, and cultural entities, particularly in light of technological advancements, shaping strategies, communication, and decision-making processes. For cultural institutions like museums, reputation assumes importance due to its potential influence on perceived organizational efficacy and resource attraction (Padanyi & Gainer, 2003; Mitchell, 2015). Specifically, the museum's reputation impacts the inclinations of potential visitors to engage with its offerings and influences the decisions of donors and sponsors regarding financial support for cultural endeavors (DiMaggio, 1986; Frey & Meier, 2006; Bennett, 2017; Camarero et al., 2023). Museums are increasingly prioritizing brand and reputation management to cultivate positive associations and differentiate themselves within competitive landscapes. In this context, online communication emerges as a crucial tool for audience engagement, visit planning, donor attraction, and stakeholder relationship building.*

Despite extensive discourse in the literature, a shared definition of reputation remains elusive. One prominent definition in managerial studies characterizes reputation as "a perceptual representation of a company's past action and future prospects that describes the firm's overall appeal to its key constituents when compared to other leading rivals" (Fombrun, 1996, p. 72). This definition, further expanded upon by various scholars, recognizes that reputation can be associated with stable and long-lasting perceptions both from external and internal stakeholders, difficult to manipulate and control by the organization and leading to comparisons with others (Wartick, 2002; Brown et al., 2006; Rhee & Haunschild, 2006; Walker, 2010).

With the advent of the digital revolution, the notion of reputation has extended to encompass the online dimension through terms such as "online reputation", "digital reputation", "web reputation", "social media reputation" and "e-

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reputation” (Cooke et al., 2022). Online reputation pertains to the ‘stakeholders’ perceptions of the organization, communicated via online platforms and social media based on their experiences (Reuber & Fisher, 2011; Diana-Jens and Ruibal, 2015).

In the context of museums, reputation serves as a fundamental element of intangible assets, facilitating differentiation in competitive environments (Solima, 2022). Van Riel (2019) posits that museums can enhance their reputation by emphasizing familiarity, historical significance, and their impact on the reputation of the city and country in which they are located. To bolster familiarity, museums can employ targeted, direct, and dialogical communication strategies. Within this framework, online communication assumes pivotal importance for museums in audience development and stakeholder engagement. Online channels serve as platforms for museums to connect with current and potential visitors, supporters, partners, and so on (Mateos-Rusillo, 2019). This digital dimension of reputation is underscored by stakeholders sharing their museum experiences through online reviews, blogs, and comments, thereby influencing collective perceptions of reputation. Consequently, museums utilize online institutional communication not only to foster audience growth but also to shape stakeholder perceptions regarding their actions and prospects, thus contributing to their reputation. Online presence, coupled with visibility, thus emerges as a key determinant shaping the collective perception of reputation over time.

Purpose of the paper. Although offline and online reputations hold significant importance for museums, research in this domain remains still in its early stages. To address this gap, this research presents a preliminary exploration of the literature on museums’ reputation with a twofold objective: (1) review the literature debate on reputation and museums’ online reputation; (2) construct a framework from the literature review for exploring the online reputation of the Uffizi Galleries, one of the most visited museums in Italy, located in the city of art of Florence. The Uffizi Galleries represent one of the oldest museum complexes in the world and group together the historical art collections of the Medici family. It is a state museum that in 2015 gained special autonomy. It has five museum sites - the Uffizi Gallery, the Drawings and Prints Cabinet and Library, the Palazzo Pitti Museum, the Vasari Corridor, and the Boboli Gardens – located in the UNESCO area of the city of Florence. Since 2016, the Uffizi has been provided by the director with a new department dedicated to IT and Digital Strategies. According to data from the Italian Ministry of Culture, the Uffizi Galleries was the most visited state museum institution in Italy in 2021 and counted the highest number of followers on social media in 2021 and 2022. Adding up all social channels - Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok - the ‘Galleries’ followers exceeded one million in December 2022, with an increase of 12.8% compared to 2021 (Il Giornale dell’arte & The Art Newspaper, 2023). Considering these characteristics, recently, it was the object of analyses and research devoted to understanding digital strategies and changes in the organization over time (Lazzeretti et al., 2024; Giusti, 2024). Based on such consideration, the Uffizi Galleries can represent a valuable case study for investigating its online dimension, visibility, image, and ultimately, reputation.

Methodology. The present research focuses on the reputation of the Uffizi Galleries by analyzing the online public discourse using text mining techniques via Python. Based on the definition of reputation and online reputation, the research develops an exploratory analysis for investigating the mental associations that external international audiences have concerning the Uffizi Galleries. The source of data was a highly relevant international newspaper, namely The New York Times.

The newspaper was chosen over other online media channels because it shapes collective and individual perceptions through the priming of existing schematic representations, the development of new representations, the integration with broader schemata or in more general narratives, indirect influence through selective re-telling in social interactions, and is a proxy for public opinions (DiMaggio et al., 2013). Moreover, empirical analyses show that media coverage records and influences public knowledge and can influence organizational reputation (Deephouse, 2000). Finally, in the literature, several contributions analyze The New York Times articles to explore the public perceptions and opinions, specifically regarding the image and reputation perceptions (Dennis, 2002; Shi et al., 2023).

The dataset of articles considered consists of $n=143$ articles published from January 1, 2016, to December 31, 2023, retrieved using the keyword “Uffizi” searched in the articles’ text. The initial date coincides with the starting of the new organizational structure related to the museum’s autonomy, while the final date coincides with the ending of the first director’s mandate. The database was established through web scraping techniques, i.e., “automated extraction of information online” (Luscombe et al., 2022), via Python programming language and, specifically, the Selenium library. Such techniques are used by various disciplines within the social sciences, such as economics (Massimino, 2016; Cavallo, 2018), organization (Braun et al., 2018), policy (Caruana-Galizia & Caruana-Galizia, 2018; Hayes & Scott, 2018) and communication (Possler et al., 2019) for collecting big amounts of data from online sources. For each article, using the data scraping technique, the following information was obtained: the title, the date of publication, the link to the article, and the body of the article.

As the digital text collected counted a large amount of data, automated methods were supposed to be the most useful methodology to analyze it. In particular, text mining techniques can be employed to derive reputation perceptions from textual content (Ghose et al., 2009; Amigó et al., 2013) using different methods (Rodriguez-Vidal et al., 2021). One of the most diffused text mining techniques is topic modelling, which consists of probabilistic models used to automatically discover topics in a corpus of texts in digital format (Blei et al., 2003). What it is possible to get from these algorithms, regardless of the model used, are two outputs: the probability that a word belongs to a certain topic and the probability that this topic emerges from a certain document.

Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) is the most widely used topic modelling technique and allows the exploration of the latent structure of textual corpora. Topics are “latent” because they are not explicitly reported by the text author (Saxton,

2018). The LDA algorithm iterates through the text and records patterns of co-occurrences in an unsupervised manner. It is thus a technique designed to capture novel and emergent ideas and cognitive content in general. This is because they reveal the conceptual relationships in the textual data, as the language used in documents represents their cognitive content (Whorf, 1956).

Firstly, the text (including both the title and the body of the article) was pre-processed using classical text mining techniques procedures to make it analyzable by the computer program. For the text pre-processing phase, the following Python libraries were used: NLTK, Pandas, Scikit-learn and NumPy.

More specifically, the text pre-processing involved the following steps:

- The text was converted to lowercase in order to avoid redundancy;
- Stopwords were removed (words that occur with high frequency but have little semantic content);
- Stemming, or vocabulary reduction, achieved by replacing words (tokens) with their own root (suffix removal);
- special characters, numbers, short tokens (words with one or two characters), and extra whitespace were removed;
- The tf-idf analysis was conducted, which assigns greater weight to words that are important in a specific document but uncommon in the entire document collection (Salton & McGill, 1983). The words with a tf-idf lower than 0.01, a threshold commonly considered significant for analysis, were removed;
- Finally, words tokenization was processed, which consisted of taking the single words as a unit of analysis.

After the pre-processing of the text, the final database was composed of 106 news articles.

Gensim was the library mainly used to conduct the subsequent steps of the analysis. As LDA algorithm is unsupervised, it was necessary to select a number of topics for the algorithm to find. To do that, coherence measures were calculated, which provide the degree of semantic similarity among words with the highest values (in the case of the LDA model, membership probability) in a topic. Thus, they indicate how well those words support the topic to which they belong. The higher the consistency, the more meaningful the topic. These measures have been shown to have a high degree of correlation with manual classifications of words to topics made by human evaluators. The three most used coherence measures were calculated in order to compare their results and select the best one: Normalized Pointwise Mutual Information (NPMI), Pointwise Mutual Information (UCI) and Umass (Röder et al. 2015). We selected 9 topics, as less than 6 topics were considered too limited (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Number of topics and coherence score. Source: authors' elaboration

Then, we applied the LDA algorithm, calculating the "eta" values per word, which represents the probability of each word per each topic.

Since the obtained structure of topics is latent, the algorithm does not automatically label the distribution of topics. Therefore, we proceeded to interpret and label the topics manually (Mohr & Bogdanov, 2013). Finally, to limit the confirmation bias and allow triangulation of the data, the results of the analysis were compared with data and information collected by primary sources – 13 interviews with managers and staff of the Uffizi Galleries and a period of participant observations in the institution – and secondary sources – specifically report on the museum visitors, website and social media.

Preliminary Results. Based on the analysis of the literature and the reputation and online reputation concept, the analysis identified the mental associations that external audiences have of the Uffizi through the identification of the main topics of discussion within The New York Times's articles.

From the topic modelling analysis, the following topics have emerged: the use of new technologies by the museum complex, the issue of queues to access museum spaces, the case of environmentalist protests in museums, the relationship and comparison with the Louvre in Paris, the Italian State Museums Reform for give autonomy to the Galleries (Riforma

Franceschini), artworks stolen by the Nazis, the restoration function, temporary exhibitions, and the relevance of the museum complex's heritage, famous and representative of Italy. The results can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of topic modelling on The New York Times dataset..

Topic 1 "Digital Technologies"		Topic 2 "Queues at the entrance"		Topic 3 "Environmental activists"		Topic 4 "Relationship with the Louvre"		Topic 5 "Franceschini Reform"		Topic 6 "Stolen artworks during the war"		Topic 7 "The restoration function"		Topic 8 "Loans of works of art"		Topic 9 "Importance of the museum's collection"	
Word	Eta	Word	Eta	Word	Eta	Word	Eta	Word	Eta	Word	Eta	Word	Eta	Word	Eta	Word	Eta
work	0.016	wait	0.040	protest	0.014	lisa	0.025	italian	0.017	paint	0.021	restor	0.020	botticelli	0.031	paint	0.016
galleri	0.014	tell	0.020	citi	0.014	mona	0.024	cultur	0.016	verrocchio	0.018	art	0.014	draw	0.018	galleri	0.013
artist	0.013	peopl	0.015	london	0.010	art	0.021	director	0.016	artist	0.012	itali	0.014	art	0.018	work	0.012
collect	0.012	king	0.015	sunflow	0.010	galleri	0.015	itali	0.016	german	0.009	artist	0.014	paint	0.016	art	0.012
art	0.012	stori	0.015	itali	0.010	louv	0.014	reform	0.011	germani	0.009	artwork	0.014	schmidt	0.014	itali	0.011
nft	0.011	line	0.010	gogh	0.010	paint	0.014	art	0.011	world	0.009	botticelli	0.007	artist	0.011	famou	0.008
visit	0.009	past	0.010	soup	0.010	think	0.009	michel	0.010	stolen	0.009	galleri	0.007	includ	0.009	restor	0.008
ostiglio	0.009	statu	0.010	van	0.010	visitor	0.009	minist	0.010	design	0.009	renaiss	0.007	work	0.009	women	0.008
world	0.007	walk	0.010	jar	0.010	work	0.008	foreign	0.010	medici	0.009	institut	0.007	figur	0.008	state	0.007
selfi	0.007	watch	0.010	work	0.007	peopl	0.008	ministri	0.009	renaiss	0.009	world	0.007	show	0.008	leonardo	0.007

Source: authors' elaboration

Regarding the first topic, the use of new technologies by the Uffizi, words related to the digitization of the Galleries' art collections have emerged, particularly for the creation and sale of NFTs. Then there is the word "selfi" which is the root of "selfie" related to the use of social media by visitors and the museum complex itself, including in relation to influencers who take photos in front of the artworks. The second topic concerns the queues that form for entry into the Uffizi. The words connected to this are "wait", "line", "people". Other words are linked to a particular article about how the author-journalist skipped the line feeling like a "king" while people "watched" him. The third topic is about environmentalist protests targeting cultural heritage to convey messages against policies that do not help reduce pollution and the destruction of nature. Protests of this kind have occurred both at the Uffizi and other major museums, such as the National Gallery in London, where Van Gogh's "Sunflowers" painting was hit with soup. Words related to this episode are found within the identified topic. The fourth topic concerns conceptual proximity and, thus, the comparison between the Uffizi Galleries and the Louvre. For example, we can find words related to Leonardo's Mona Lisa. The fifth topic is about the Franceschini Reform, the reform carried out by the Italian Government in 2014 for the reorganization of the Italian Ministry of Culture and its affiliated museums. Among these is the Uffizi monumental complex, which has seen a significant reorganization of its structure and a new figure of the director at its head, with significant decision-making autonomy in its management. The sixth topic emerged concerns the theme of artworks stolen from the Uffizi collections by the Nazis during World War II. Director Eike Schmidt indeed fought for the return of a painting that the owning family did not want to return to the museum despite requests from the Italian State. The seventh topic concerns the fundamental function of restoring works from the collection, with reference to those by Botticelli. The eighth topic is about temporary exhibitions, such as the "Botticelli Drawings" exhibition at the Department of Drawings and Prints of the Fine Art Museums of San Francisco, to which the Uffizi lent numerous works. Finally, the ninth topic reflects on the importance of the artworks and paintings of the Uffizi, which are representative of Italian heritage and are famous worldwide.

From a general perspective, preliminary results of the analysis show that the mental associations of external audiences concerning the Uffizi Galleries emerged from the analysis of The New York Times article pertain to several categories. Firstly, some topics that constitute the museum's reputation relate to traditional aspects of museums' management. These topics involve discourse on the valuable collections belonging to the museum, the interest in artwork restoration and specific temporary exhibitions, and the comparison with other important international museums, such as the Louvre. Moreover, some critical aspects emerge related to the visitors' management, especially regarding long waiting times in line to enter the museum. Secondly, other relevant topics closely related to the contemporary role of museums in society emerge, such as the use of digital technologies, the theme of environmental activism and the role of museums, and the impact of war on artworks belonging to all of humanity. The results from the text mining analysis are confirmed by the qualitative analysis, particularly by the content of interviews with managers and staff. As has emerged from interviews, these topics are felt to be central to the museum, which aims to position itself as a stimulator and space for sharing reflections on important social themes through its own collection, which serves as a catalyst.

Research limitations. The research presents several limitations. First, a single newspaper cannot be considered exhaustive in representing the reputation of the Uffizi Galleries and, thus, all perceptions expressed in public discourses. Further research will consider data coming from other newspapers, social media platforms, forums, and review platforms to have a more complete view of the different forms of public discourses and audiences. Moreover, in terms of the chosen methodology, sentiment analysis of the considered texts was not conducted, which could provide information on how the identified themes contribute positively, neutrally, or negatively to the museum's reputation. Future research, in line with what has emerged in the literature on the detection of organizations' online reputations, can address these limitations.

Managerial implications. The museum's online activities and the online public discourse play an important role in constructing the organization's reputation. Reputation can be considered a strategic asset for organizations, even museums, in order to increase their competitive advantage. Measuring and managing a museum's reputation, in fact, may increase potential visitors and influence the donors' and sponsors' attitudes towards funding cultural activities. Monitoring and evaluating online public discourse through newspapers and mass media may constitute a strategy for

identifying the main attributes associated with the organization and assessing the sentiment of public opinion on the organizational reputation. Monitoring online newspapers allows organizations to understand public sentiment and proactively manage their reputation, by identifying emerging issues or negative perceptions in advance and implementing corrective actions promptly to mitigate potential damage to their reputation. Moreover, cultural organization and museums can trace the contents that resonate in the public debate and develop strategies to increase their visibility, with consequences on their performance in terms of visitors and revenue.

Originality of the paper. Although several researchers have underlined the importance of the reputation concept for organizations, few empirical analyses have been devoted to exploring the topic in the context of museums (Chung et al., 2019; Van Riel, 2019; Fernández-Hernández et al., 2021). The originality of the research can be traced both for the theoretical discussion and the empirical application. Concerning the theoretical discussion, the research is original in the tentative of merging the theories of reputation in management and organizational studies with the studies of museum management. Moreover, in empirical terms, the research enlarges the debate on museum reputation with an original study on the Uffizi Galleries reputation, using an original dataset constructed ad hoc for the analysis. Previous research on the Uffizi Galleries and the digital dimensions was interested in investigating the museum business model and digital strategy. To the best of our knowledge, no previous studies of museum organizations apply text mining, and in particular topic modelling, for assessing the reputation of museums using data from online newspapers.

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